

Does real time experience matter? Comparison of retrospective and in situ spatial data in participatory mapping

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Summary

The aim of this study is to reveal whether and how retrospective and in situ data collected in the process of Participatory GIS differ. This well suited technique serves for mapping the spatial aspects of an individual's perception, and can be carried out from previous experiences (retrospectively), or directly as people go about their routine activities (in situ). The current study compares maps of people's perceptions of urban space in Olomouc city, Czech Republic and in Manchester, UK using both approaches. Evaluating how conclusions differ between these approaches contributes to better understanding and interpretation of geospatial participatory data in future.

KEYWORDS: Participatory GIS, Perception, Urban Space, Map-Me, CIN CITY

1. Introduction

Geospatial data obtained through participatory mapping represent a valuable source of information in various disciplines such as urban planning (Pánek, 2019), mapping of fear of crime (Šimáček et al., 2021) or investigation of segregation (Huck et al., 2019). PPGIS (Public Participatory GIS) represents one of the most common approaches to participatory mapping and is mostly used for gathering retrospective information from participants about their environment allowing better citizens' engagement in decision making processes (Haklay, 2013). Several PPGIS approaches attempt to apply also in situ data models which offer certain advantages over examining more traditional retrospective data (Solymosi et al., 2021).

1.1. Retrospective vs. in situ data

In the participatory mapping process we can capture two basic types of data – retrospective and in situ (real-time/real-place) data. Retrospective data are based on an individual's past experiences, while its opposite – in situ data are reported at the moment of occurrence, not after. Some studies argue that common retrospective approaches have some significant drawbacks such as under/overestimating of experiences (Ben-Zeev et al., 2012). In order to provide a more accurate and detailed description of situations in an individual's life, methods based on capturing everyday experience data should be applied as they examine behaviour in its natural and spontaneous environment (Reis et al. 2000). In contrast with retrospective approaches, everyday/momentary/in situ data about environment collected in real time and at a real place can be gathered from participants using mobile smartphone applications (Kronkvist & Engström, 2020; Solymosi et al., 2021).

This might be quantitative (e.g. mapping pollution exposure; Huck et al., 2017) or qualitative data (e.g. mapping fear of crime; Chataway et al., 2017). Some of the existing participatory mobile applications enable capturing both in situ and retrospective information about perception (e.g. Solymosi et al., 2015);

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some provide only a ‘near’ retrospective option (e.g. the past 24 hours; Kronkvist & Engström, 2020), and others are limited to real-time collection, and do not collect retrospective experiences at all (e.g. Buil-Gil, 2016).

However, little is known about differences between the collection of real-time and retrospective data in Participatory GIS. This paper seeks to fill this gap by revealing whether there are any differences when mapping the same spatial information relating to an individual’s perception of space retrospectively (using a PPGIS) and in real-time (using a mobile app).

2. Case study

This paper will focus on data collected in Olomouc, Czech Republic. It is the largest city in the eponymous (Olomouc) region located in eastern part of the Czech Republic (Figure 1). It has a population of 97,993 with an above average proportion of young people who are often attracted by the third biggest Czech university which is based in Olomouc city (MVCR, 2022).

Figure 1 Olomouc city and its localisation within Europe

3. Applied methods

The most fundamental part of the study is the two-phase method model which has been used to reveal differences between retrospective and in situ participatory data. A sample of 258 participants from Olomouc city participated in the first – retrospective data collection phase in July-November 2021. The PPGIS survey was created using Map-Me platform (Huck et al., 2014). Participants answered a set of simple demographic questions, before using the ‘spraycan’ (airbrush) mapping interface to ‘spray paint’ on to the map relating to their perception of Olomouc (Figure 2). Participants were asked to identify areas that they felt were:

- Topophilic = pleasant
- Topophobic = unpleasant
- Topovacant = abandoned or vacant places that could be treated and utilized in a better way

Figure 2 English Map Me interface used in the first phase of the research

At the end of the survey, respondents were invited to write down their email address so they could be contacted for participation in the second part of the study. 70 of 256 participants agreed to continue and participate in the second phase intended for collection of in situ data. For this purpose, we developed a mobile application CIN CITY[§] which is determined to collect data in real time, while the participant was at that location. When participants submit a new record, the application records it alongside their location (via the device’s on-board GPS receiver) and the current timestamp. When a participant records a location as topophillic, topophobic or topovacant, they are asked some contextual questions concerning intensity of this feeling, the reasons for it, and so on (Figure 3). Both surveys (in Map-Me and CIN CITY platforms) are available in both English and Czech language.

Figure 3 English CIN CITY interface used in the second phase of the research

[§] Civic Innovation in Community

All 70 respondents are inhabitants of Olomouc, and they comprise 33 women and 37 men. A closer look at the age structure from the chart in Figure 4 reveals a significant prevalence of younger respondents with the strongest share of 25–34 years old age group (41.4 %) and 18–24 years old age group (22.9 %). Participation was limited by the exclusion of iPhone users, as the CIN CITY app is only currently available on Android devices.

Figure 4 Age structure of 70 respondents

4. Preliminary results

Primary preliminary analysis of data collected by 70 participants in the first phase is displayed in Figure 5. Topophilic, topophobic and topovacant places cumulate in several clusters of concentration. Topophilic (green) areas are covering especially the central part of the city and adjacent parks. Conversely, topophobic (red) areas are typically located along major road networks, around the railway station and in city parks. Topovacant (blue) areas represent the smallest number of locations out of all three sprayed types of perception and are in many locations across the city.

Figure 5 Data collected through the web-based survey in Map-Me interface

The second phase of data (using the CIN CITY mobile application) is still ongoing, and will be analysed and presented in the updated version of this paper prior to the conference.

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